

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Sh.G. Mannanova

Senior Lecturer at Tashkent State University of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8048207>

Abstract. The article presents the results of the implementation of Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government", also analyzed the trends in the development of e-government in our country. The data of the UN rating on the level of development of e-government are presented.

Keywords: digital technologies, e-government, interactive public services, digital economy, information and communication technologies, Internet segment, Single portal of interactive public services.

Today, in our independent Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a rapid development of information and communication technologies and digital technologies. Our President Sh. Mirziyoyev has repeatedly noted this in his speeches. So April 28, 2020 In our country, the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government" No. PP-4699 was adopted. This document raised topical issues related to the widespread introduction of digital technologies in the work of domestic enterprises and government services, the training of IT specialists, comprehensive support for IT entrepreneurship, and many others.

Of course, a prerequisite for the digital development of our country is the creation of a modern telecommunications base. In this regard, over the past five years, a lot of work has been done in our republic to modernize and expand communication networks.

The development of fiber optic infrastructure, in turn, contributed to an increase in the throughput of communication channels.

During 2021-2022, 102 thousand km of fiber-optic communication lines were laid, and thus their total length was increased to 118.6 thousand kilometers. Due to this, their total length increased by 2.5 times (Fig. 1.).

Figure 1. Total length of fiber-optic communication lines (thousand km)

The subscriber base of mobile operators is consistently growing. Within five years, the number of mobile users has grown from 20.6 million in 2016 to 30.2 million as of May 1, 2022 (Figure 2.).

Figure 2. Number of mobile subscribers (million)

Also, during this time, more than 22 thousand mobile base stations were installed. The coverage of the population with cellular communication reached 99%, and with broadband mobile Internet - 98%.

An important factor in increasing the availability of the Internet for the population is the consistent reduction in prices for communication services. Over the past five years, for providers, the cost of tariffs for Internet services of external channels has decreased tenfold (Figure 3.).

Figure 3. Total number of Internet users (million)

As part of the digital development of the republic, special emphasis is placed on providing social facilities with high-speed Internet connections. At present, 97% of general education schools, 82% of mahalla gatherings of citizens, 56% of police stations, as well as 100 percent of preschool educational and medical institutions are connected to a high-speed Internet network.

The development of the e-government system in Uzbekistan is considered as one of the priority areas of digital reforms, which will allow to qualitatively reform the activities of public authorities and administration.

E-governmenta system of organizational and legal measures and technical means aimed at ensuring the activities of state bodies for the provision of public services to individuals and legal entities through the use of information and communication technologies, as well as interdepartmental electronic interaction [1].

The most important role in the development of the E-gov system is assigned to the Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services (SPIS), through which a wide range of services for the population is provided. To date, 262 types of public services are being provided through the SPIGU. Within two years, it is planned to introduce another 135 new ones, as well as to simplify 100 types of electronic public services.

In order to create even greater convenience for citizens, a mobile version of the SPIGU has been launched, through which 36 types of electronic public services are provided today, and in the future it is planned to increase their number to one hundred.

Consistent work is underway to introduce a system for the provision of electronic public services through the SPIS in the work of postal services. The plans also include creating the possibility of access to the services of the SPSI in consular missions in foreign countries for citizens living abroad.

Further development of the e-government system implies the improvement of existing e-service systems and the greatest possible involvement of the number of citizens in digital processes. In this regard, one of the significant e-government projects is the Unified Identification System for Citizens One ID (<https://id.gov.uz/>). With its help, citizens get access to various electronic resources of the government, including through the issuance of ID-cards with the automatic creation of an owner account. To date, 80 information systems and resources of state bodies and organizations have been integrated into this system.

One of the priority tasks in the framework of the development of the e-government system is the creation of an effective mechanism for interaction between the authorities and the population with the widespread use of digital technologies.

As the figures clearly demonstrate, the digitalization of the public sector has made it possible to increase the efficiency of government agencies. The following successes have been achieved:

- thanks to the introduction of the Electronic Labor Book system, about 2.1 billion soums were saved;
- more than 146.4 thousand people were provided with jobs through the National Job Base;
- through the system of the Unified Register of Social Protection, social assistance was issued to more than 1 million families;
- more than 1.7 million certificates were digitized through the information system "Electronic passport";
- through the information system "Youth notebook", more than 55.8 thousand people were provided with work, 23.2 thousand people started their own business, 26.5 thousand were trained in their specialty, 133.5 thousand received land resources for the organization of a dehqan farm , 15.6 thousand received social, financial and psychological support from the state.

Digital technologies are also being actively introduced into the private sector. Thus, thanks to the introduction of the Digital Bank system, the number of Internet banking users has grown to 16.8 million people. and the number of online cards reached 20.1 million units.

In the UN rating on the level of development of e-government in 2022, Uzbekistan rose by 18 positions and took 69th place among 193 countries (Table 1).

The countries of the former USSR in the e-government development rating:

Table 1

A country	Position (2022)	Ball (2022)	Position (2020)	Ball (2020)
Kazakhstan	28	0.8628	29	0.8375
Russia	42	0.8162	36	0.8244
Ukraine	46	0.8029	69	0.7119
Belarus	58	0.7580	40	0.8084
Georgia	60	0.7501	65	0.7174
Armenia	64	0.7364	68	0.7136
Uzbekistan	69	0.7265	87	0.6665
Moldova	72	0.7251	79	0.6881
Kyrgyzstan	81	0.6977	83	0.6749
Azerbaijan	83	0.6937	70	0.7100
Tajikistan	129	0.5039	133	0.4649
Turkmenistan	137	0.4808	158	0.4034

This rating is compiled every two years, and the position of each country is formed based on three sub-indices:

- online services index;
- telecommunications infrastructure index;
- human capital index.

The indicator for each of the three components, in turn, is made up of many parameters, including information services and government websites, as well as their accessibility to citizens, the relative number of Internet users, the number of users of fixed and mobile telephones, the level of literacy of the population , regulatory framework and other factors.

e-Government Development Index (EGDI)Uzbekistan has risen by 0.06 points in two years and is now equal to 0.7265. This is well above both the global average of 0.61 and the Asian average of 0.65.

By comparison, Denmark scored 0.97, while South Korea, Asia's leader, scored 0.95.

In the telecommunications infrastructure sub-index, Uzbekistan improved the most, to 0.6575. For online services, the score was 0.7440, and for human capital it was 0.7778.

At the same time, the electronic participation index (EPI) in the new report fell to 0.61. If in 2020 Uzbekistan ranked 46th in this indicator, now it is only 55th.

Thus, in conclusion, we can conclude that the weakest component of the e-government index in Uzbekistan for 2022 is the e-participation index (EPI), when the development index of telecommunications infrastructure, online services and human capital, on the contrary, contributes to an increase in the development indicators of the concept digital government in our country.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic Uzbekistan on e-government of December 9, 2015.
2. Ministry of Information technologies and communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Electronic resource* : <http://mitc.uz>.-
3. e-government *Republic of Uzbekistan*. *Electronic resource* <https://gov.uz>. <https://gov.uz>.
4. Portal interactive *public services of the Republic of Uzbekistan*. *Electronic resource*: <https://my.gov.uz>.
5. Mannanova Sh.G. Analysis of the development of e-government in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Journal ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS theory and practice, DOI: 10.24411/2411-0450-2018-10135
6. Mannanova Shakhida, Jumaniyazova Muqaddas, Avalova Gulshod . World experience of digital platform development trends. Journal of Critical Reviews, 2020/5
7. Mannanova Sh.G. The main issues of development of IT-technologies in Uzbekistan. Journal ECONOMY AND BUSINESS theory and practice. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osnovnye-voprosy-razvitiya-it-tehnologiy-v-uzbekistane/viewer>
8. Mannanova Sh.G, Belalova G. A., Trends in the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan. Journal «SCIENCE AND INNOVATION». International Scientific journal volume 2 issue 5 may 2023, UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 | SCIENTISTS.UZ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7904842>